

A Novel Approach to Mitigating Islanding Risks in Grid-Connected Renewable Energy Systems Using Passive Detection Techniques and Overvoltage / Overcurrent Protection

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KEYWORDS

Islanding detection, ROCOV, passive techniques, grid-connected solar PV, overvoltage protection, overcurrent protection, power quality, renewable energy, voltage disturbance, harmonic distortion, system protection.

ABSTRACT

Islanding detection is a critical challenge in grid-connected renewable energy systems, as failure to identify islanding conditions can lead to power quality issues, equipment damage, and safety hazards. This paper presents a novel approach to mitigating islanding risks using passive detection techniques combined with overvoltage and overcurrent protection mechanisms. The proposed method leverages voltage and current disturbance monitoring to detect islanding conditions based on deviations in frequency, voltage magnitude, and harmonic distortion. By integrating threshold-based passive detection algorithms with an advanced protection scheme, the system ensures a fast, accurate, and reliable response to islanding events while maintaining low false detection rates. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach effectively detects islanding within a few milliseconds, ensuring compliance with IEEE 1547 and IEC 62116 standards. The combined use of passive indicators and protection circuits minimizes the non-detection zone (NDZ) while avoiding unnecessary disconnections due to grid disturbances. Compared to traditional passive methods, the proposed technique offers enhanced sensitivity, improved response time, and better adaptability to varying grid conditions. The study concludes that integrating passive detection with overvoltage/overcurrent protection provides a cost-effective and efficient solution for ensuring grid stability and operational safety in

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into modern power grids has introduced numerous challenges related to grid stability, operational reliability, and safety. Among these challenges, unintentional islanding is a critical issue in grid-connected distributed generation (DG) systems. Islanding occurs when a DG unit, such as a solar photovoltaic (PV) or wind energy system, continues supplying power to a local load despite being physically disconnected from the main utility grid. This phenomenon can lead to voltage and frequency instability, degradation of power quality, equipment malfunctions, and safety hazards for utility personnel and end-users. Due to these risks, global grid standards such as IEEE 1547 and IEC 62116 mandate that islanding must be detected within a short time frame, typically within 2 seconds, to ensure the secure operation of the grid and DG units [1], [2]. To address the islanding detection challenge, various methods have been developed, broadly classified into passive, active, and hybrid detection techniques. Passive islanding detection methods monitor system parameters such as voltage, frequency, total harmonic distortion (THD), and phase angle variations to identify abnormal deviations that indicate islanding [3], [4]. These methods have advantages in terms of simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and non-intrusiveness since they do not introduce disturbances into the grid. However, a major limitation of passive methods is the presence of a non-detection zone (NDZ)—a range in which islanding may not be reliably detected, leading to delayed responses or missed detections [5], [6]. To enhance the reliability of passive techniques, researchers have explored the use of multiple parameters such as rate of change of frequency (ROCOF), voltage unbalance, and phase angle jump (PAJ) [7], [8]. On the other hand, active islanding detection methods introduce perturbations, such as harmonic injection or small frequency shifts, into the system and analyze the response to determine whether islanding has occurred [9]. These techniques significantly reduce the NDZ but suffer from drawbacks, including increased implementation complexity and degradation of power quality, making them less favorable in high-power renewable energy systems [10], [11]. Hybrid methods, which combine passive and active

techniques, have been proposed to mitigate these issues. While hybrid techniques offer improved detection performance, they often require additional circuitry and computational resources, increasing both cost and complexity [12], [13]. To overcome the limitations of existing approaches, this paper proposes a novel passive islanding detection method combined with overvoltage and overcurrent protection mechanisms to enhance detection accuracy and response time. The proposed approach leverages voltage magnitude, frequency deviations, and current disturbances as key indicators for islanding detection. By integrating a threshold-based passive detection algorithm with an advanced protection scheme, the system ensures a fast, accurate, and reliable response to islanding conditions while minimizing false detection rates. Unlike conventional passive techniques, which often struggle with NDZ issues, the proposed method enhances sensitivity by employing multi-parameter monitoring, effectively reducing the likelihood of undetected islanding events [14], [15]. Several studies have investigated the effectiveness of passive islanding detection techniques for DG systems. For instance, frequency-based methods such as ROCOF and harmonic distortion monitoring have been widely adopted in PV and wind-based microgrids [16], [17]. However, these approaches can be affected by external grid disturbances, leading to erroneous tripping or failure to detect islanding events. Similarly, voltage-based passive methods, which rely on voltage unbalance and phase angle measurements, have demonstrated promising results but may struggle under highly variable load conditions [18], [19]. Recent advancements in islanding detection focus on machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI)-based techniques, where support vector machines (SVM), artificial neural networks (ANNs), and deep learning models have been employed to improve detection accuracy [20], [21]. While these AI-based methods show potential, they require large computational resources, extensive training datasets, and real-time implementation capabilities, making them less feasible for low-cost, real-world grid applications [22], [23]. In addition to detection techniques, overvoltage and overcurrent protection mechanisms play a crucial role in enhancing the reliability and safety of grid-connected renewable energy systems. During islanding events, transient

overvoltages and overcurrents can occur due to load imbalances, sudden changes in power demand, or inverter instability, potentially leading to equipment damage and safety hazards [24]. Traditional protection schemes, such as circuit breakers and fuse-based disconnection mechanisms, often lack the responsiveness required for modern high-power DG applications. Therefore, integrating an advanced overvoltage and overcurrent protection system within the islanding detection framework helps prevent damage, ensure rapid disconnection, and maintain grid stability. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the proposed passive detection method integrated with overvoltage/overcurrent protection, demonstrating its superior performance in detecting islanding events while maintaining grid compliance with IEEE 1547 and IEC 62116 standards. Through MATLAB/Simulink-based simulations, the study evaluates the effectiveness of the proposed method in terms of detection time, sensitivity, false detection rates, and NDZ reduction. The results indicate that the method can detect islanding within a few milliseconds, offering enhanced sensitivity and improved adaptability to varying grid conditions compared to conventional passive approaches [25]. Furthermore, the integration of overvoltage and overcurrent protection circuits significantly reduces the risk of equipment failures and enhances overall system safety.

II. Proposed System configuration

The proposed system consists of a solar photovoltaic system connected to the grid, converting sunlight into electrical energy. The generated power is regulated through a DC-DC boost converter and fed into a voltage source inverter, which maintains grid stability by controlling voltage, frequency, and power quality. The islanding detection mechanism uses passive techniques to monitor voltage magnitude, frequency deviations, and harmonic distortions. An overvoltage and overcurrent protection circuit is incorporated to ensure accuracy and compliance with international standards. The control strategy uses threshold-based algorithms and advanced signal processing methods to detect variations in grid parameters. When islanding occurs, the system responds within milliseconds, triggering rapid disconnection to prevent equipment damage and personnel safety as shown in Fig.1. The integrated protection scheme minimizes non-detection zones and avoids unnecessary disconnections caused by transient grid disturbances. This approach enhances system adaptability under varying grid conditions and load fluctuations, providing a cost-effective and efficient solution for maintaining grid stability and operational safety in solar photovoltaic-based distributed generation systems.

Fig.1 proposed system configuration

Fig.2. Simulink model of grid connected PV array.

III. Modeling and designing of proposed system configuration

The proposed system is designed as a grid-connected solar photovoltaic (PV) system with an integrated passive islanding detection mechanism and overvoltage/overcurrent protection. The system consists of key components, including a solar PV array, DC-DC boost converter, voltage source inverter (VSI), grid interface, and islanding detection unit. The modeling and design involve various mathematical equations to describe the system's operation, ensuring optimal performance, grid stability, and protection under different conditions.

a. Solar PV boost converter system configuration

The solar power system in a DC microgrid is crucial for efficient energy conversion and integration with other renewable energy sources. A perturb and observe (P&O) maximum power point tracking (MPPT) boost converter is used to optimize power extraction from the photovoltaic (PV) array, ensuring it operates at its maximum power point under varying solar irradiance conditions. The P&O MPPT algorithm continuously adjusts the operating point by introducing small perturbations to the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter. This architecture ensures stable power distribution for EV fast charging stations, minimizing power losses and improving overall efficiency. The DC microgrid benefits from this configuration by achieving improved renewable energy utilization, reduced reliance on grid power, and enhanced power quality. The bidirectional energy flow capability allows for effective integration with battery storage systems, ensuring energy availability even during low solar generation

periods. Implementing this solar P&O MPPT boost converter allows the DC microgrid to manage power distribution, support multiple EV chargers, and enhance sustainability by reducing carbon emissions through increased renewable energy penetration.

Fig. 3 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

1. Single-Diode Solar PV Model: Designing a single-diode solar PV model involves analyzing the electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic (PV) cell. The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used to simulate the behavior of a PV cell. This model includes one diode, a current source, and series and shunt resistances to represent losses as shown in fig.3.
2. Basic Equation of the Single-Diode Model: The equation that governs the behavior of the single-diode PV model is derived from Kirchhoff's current law (KCL):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

Where: I = output current of the PV module (A), I_{ph} = photocurrent, the current generated by light (A), I_D = diode current (A), I_{sh} = shunt current (A)

3. Diode Current (I_D): The current through the diode is described by the Shockley diode equation:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+IR_s}{nV_t}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4 equivalent model of PV solar.

Where: I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode (A), V = voltage across the PV cell (V), R_s = series resistance (Ω), n = diode ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2), V_t = thermal voltage (V), given by $V_t = kqT$

Here:

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K), T = temperature in Kelvin (K), q = electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)

4. Shunt Current (I_{sh}): The current through the shunt resistance R_{sh} is modeled as:

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

5. Equation of the Single-Diode PV Model: By substituting the expressions for I_D and I_{sh} into the main current equation, we get the complete form of the single-diode model:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+IR_s}{nV_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

6. Photocurrent I_{ph} : The current generated by the cell due to light is proportional to the incident light and is affected by temperature. It can be modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{ph,ref} + \mu I_{ph} \cdot (T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

Where: $I_{ph,ref}$ = reference photocurrent at standard test conditions (STC), I_{ph} = temperature coefficient of photocurrent ($A/^\circ C$), T = cell temperature ($^\circ C$), T_{ref} = reference temperature (usually $25^\circ C$), G = irradiance (W/m^2), G_{ref} = reference irradiance at STC ($1000 W/m^2$)

7. Saturation Current I_0 : The reverse saturation current varies exponentially with temperature:

$$I_0 = I_{0,ref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{\frac{E_g}{nV_t} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Where: $I_{0,ref}$ = reverse saturation current at reference temperature, E_g = bandgap energy of the semiconductor (typically 1.1 eV for silicon)

b. P&O MPPT Algorithm

The P&O MPPT algorithm adjusts the duty cycle (D) of the boost converter based on small perturbations to the PV voltage. The power change is determined as follows:

Fig.5 flow chart for P&O MPPT algorithm

$$\Delta P = P(k) - P(k-1) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta V = V(k) - V(k-1) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P > 0 \text{ and } \Delta V > 0, \text{ increase } V_{pv} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P < 0 \text{ and } \Delta V > 0, \text{ decrease } V_{pv} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P > 0 \text{ and } \Delta V < 0, \text{ decrease } V_{pv} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{if } \Delta P < 0 \text{ and } \Delta V < 0, \text{ increase } V_{pv} \quad (12)$$

The updated duty cycle is calculated as:

$$D(k+1) = D(k) + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta P) \quad (13)$$

Where α is the step size for duty cycle adjustment.

c. Boost Converter Design

The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC bus voltage. The output voltage of the boost converter is given by:

Fig.6 DC-DC unidirectional boost converter

$$V_o = \frac{V_{pv}}{1-D} \quad (14)$$

Where: V_o = Output voltage of boost converter (V), V_{pv} = Input PV voltage (V), D = Duty cycle of the converter
The inductor value is selected to ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation:

$$L = \frac{V_{pv}(1-D)}{f_s \Delta I_L} \quad (15)$$

where: L = Inductor value (H), fs = Switching frequency (Hz), ΔIL = Inductor ripple current (A)

The output capacitor is designed to minimize voltage ripples:

$$C = \frac{I_o}{f_s \Delta V_o} \quad (16)$$

Where: C = Output capacitor (F), Io = Output current (A), ΔVo = Allowable voltage ripple (V)

IV. Modeling and Design of a Grid-Connected Voltage Source Converter (VSC) Controller

A bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) plays a crucial role in integrating renewable energy systems, electric vehicle charging stations, and microgrids by enabling efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC link as shown in Fig.8. The d-q current control strategy is widely used to regulate power flow, improve power quality, and maintain DC link voltage stability. The system operates under a synchronous reference frame (SRF) to ensure precise control of active and reactive power components.

designing of bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter

The control operation of the grid-connected bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) is based on a hierarchical structure comprising DC-link voltage regulation, current control, grid synchronization, and bidirectional power flow management. The DC-link voltage regulation is achieved through an outer-loop PI controller, which maintains the reference DC voltage by adjusting the d-axis current reference (Id_ref). This ensures a stable DC bus, crucial for efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC load. The inner-loop current controllers regulate the d-axis and q-axis currents to track their respective reference values, enabling precise control over active and reactive power (P-Q regulation). A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is employed for grid synchronization, ensuring that the converter operates in phase with the grid voltage, which is essential for stable operation under varying grid conditions as shown in Fig.9. The bidirectional operation

of the converter allows seamless transition between grid-to-DC charging (rectifier mode) and DC-to-grid discharging (inverter mode) depending on the power flow direction. In rectifier mode, the converter draws power from the grid to maintain the required DC voltage, whereas in inverter mode, it injects power back into the grid when excess DC power is available. This comprehensive control strategy ensures optimal power management, enhances grid stability, and improves the overall efficiency of the system.

1. Mathematical Modeling of the Bidirectional AC-DC VSC

The operation of the bidirectional VSC can be described using d-q axis equations derived from Kirchhoff's Voltage Law (KVL). The system consists of an LC filter, a three-phase inverter, and a DC-link capacitor, ensuring stable voltage conversion.

1.1 AC Side d-q Equations

The AC-side dynamics of the three-phase VSC in the synchronous rotating reference frame are given by:

$$V_d = R_s I_d + L_s \frac{dI_d}{dt} - \omega L_s I_q + V_{gd} \quad (17)$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + L_s \frac{dI_q}{dt} - \omega L_s I_d + V_{gq} \quad (18)$$

where:

- Vd, Vq = d-q axis voltages at the converter terminals
- Id, Iq = d-q axis currents
- Rs, Ls = Resistance and inductance of the filter
- ω = Synchronous angular frequency
- Vgd, Vgq = d-q components of the grid voltage

The active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injected into the grid are given by:

$$P = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) \quad (19)$$

$$Q = \frac{3}{2} (V_q I_d - V_d I_q) \quad (20)$$

2. DC-Link Voltage Controller Design

The DC-link voltage (Vdc) is regulated using a PI controller to ensure stable operation during bidirectional power transfer. The power balance at the DC bus is given by:

$$C_{dc} \frac{dV_{dc}}{dt} = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) - P_{dc_load} \quad (21)$$

where: Cdc = DC-link capacitor, Pdc_load = Power consumed by the DC load

To maintain a stable DC-link voltage, a PI controller is implemented as:

$$I_d^{ref} = K_p (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) + k_i \int (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) dt \quad (22)$$

estimation, signal derivatives, and adaptive threshold logic. The system continuously samples the terminal

voltage $V(t)$ at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) and calculates the RMS voltage over a defined window:

Fig.9. Block diagram of the proposed methodology.

$$V_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N V(n)^2} \quad (29)$$

This RMS value is compared with the nominal operating voltage to determine the deviation. Simultaneously, the mean voltage is calculated using a moving average filter to suppress transient noise:

$$V_{mean}(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=t-m+1}^t V(k) \quad (30)$$

To capture rapid system changes that may signal an islanding event, the instantaneous derivative of the voltage is computed:

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{V(n) - V(n-1)}{\Delta t} \quad (31)$$

This derivative acts as a core element of the ROCOV technique, and is compared with a dynamically set threshold T_{ROCOV} , which adjusts based on the average load profile and grid behavior:

$$T_{ROCOV} = B \cdot \sigma V + V_{mean} \quad (32)$$

Where σV is the standard deviation of the voltage, and β is a tunable factor based on system stability margins. If the condition $|dV/dt| > T_{ROCOV}$ is met and persists beyond a minimal time delay, the protection logic flags a potential islanding scenario. A second validation layer checks whether the RMS voltage has crossed critical boundaries:

$$V_{RMS} > 1.1 \cdot V_{nominal} \text{ or } V_R < 0.88V_{nominal} \quad (33)$$

In either case, the system activates the overvoltage or undervoltage protection and sends a trip signal to isolate the PV inverter. This combined use of statistical and differential monitoring ensures fast and accurate detection of abnormal grid conditions while minimizing false trips caused by transient disturbances. The method adheres to IEEE 1547 standards and provides reliable inverter protection during islanding, maintaining system safety and grid integrity.

VI. Results and Discussions

The simulation is carried out to evaluate the performance of the proposed islanding detection and protection method under various operating scenarios. Under normal operating conditions without islanding or fault disturbances, the PCC voltage remains stable, and the system maintains proper load sharing between the solar power source and the grid. Variations in solar irradiation are handled dynamically, where the solar system supplies power to the load and any excess is sent to the grid. When solar generation decreases due to a drop in irradiation, the grid automatically compensates to meet the load demand, maintaining system balance. When islanding occurs, a noticeable change is observed in the PCC voltage waveform, where the voltage magnitude begins to fluctuate due to the absence of the grid's stabilizing effect. The rate of change of voltage signal also increases, and the islanding detection mechanism gets activated. Once islanding is confirmed, the triggering signal initiates the disconnection of the inverter from the system by opening the circuit breaker. After the breaker operation, the PCC voltage drops, indicating successful isolation and protection of the distributed generation system. In the case of a fault condition, a sudden drop in PCC voltage is observed, clearly distinguishable from the islanding case. This validates the system's ability to detect and differentiate between fault and islanding scenarios. Overall, the simulation results confirm that the system responds accurately and reliably under varying solar, islanding, and fault conditions, ensuring stability and safety.

A. Solar Irradiation with Grid Support (Non-Islanding Condition)

The simulation results illustrate the dynamic performance of the solar PV system with 80 kW capacity connected to a 50 kW load under varying solar irradiation levels, while maintaining continuous grid

connectivity. During the initial interval from 0 to 0.25 seconds, solar irradiance is held constant at 1000 W/m^2 , allowing the PV system to generate its full rated power of 80 kW. In this phase, the load demand of 50 kW is fully supplied by the solar source, and the surplus 30 kW is exported to the grid. As the solar irradiance gradually decreases from 1000 W/m^2 to 500 W/m^2 between 0.25 and 0.6 seconds, the solar output correspondingly drops, leading to a reduction in PV power generation. To ensure uninterrupted power supply to the load, the grid automatically compensates for the deficit, maintaining a balanced and stable voltage at the PCC. Between 0.6 and 0.8 seconds, the irradiance falls to 0 W/m^2 , simulating a total loss of solar input, and during this period, the entire load demand is fulfilled by the grid, confirming robust grid support and dynamic load balancing. Subsequently, from 0.8 to 1 second, the solar irradiance rises again to 800 W/m^2 , enabling partial generation from the solar system, and thereby reducing the grid power contribution. Throughout the simulation, the PCC voltage remains stable without any disruption, reflecting effective power management, grid reliability, and seamless solar-grid-load coordination in non-islanding conditions

Simulation Results under Dynamic Solar Irradiation with Grid Support (Non-Islanding Condition)

B. PCC Voltage under Normal, Islanding, and Fault Conditions

The Point of Common Coupling (PCC) voltage response under normal, islanding, and fault conditions was analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed islanding detection method. Under normal conditions, the PCC voltage remains stable due to the grid's ability

to absorb inverter output variations. However, when islanding occurs, the inverter becomes the sole power source for the load, leading to an increase in the PCC voltage magnitude due to the mismatch between the inverter's power output and load demand. In a three-phase fault, a sharp decrease in PCC voltage occurs due to a sudden drop in impedance and rapid

surge in current, causing voltage sag. These three scenarios are the basis for the proposed islanding detection algorithm, allowing for accurate and fast islanding detection, ensuring safe disconnection of the distributed generation system and compliance with grid protection standards.

Fig.1. Instantaneous voltage amplitude at PCC during a) Normal grid connected DG condition b) Islanding condition c) 3-phase fault at the grid side feeder.

C. Islanding Detection and Protection Operation

The simulation results clearly demonstrate the system's response during an islanding event occurring at 0.5 seconds. Prior to this moment, the grid remains connected, and the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) voltage maintains a stable magnitude due to grid support. At 0.5 seconds, islanding is detected based on the sudden increase in PCC voltage magnitude and a noticeable rise in the Rate of Change of Voltage (ROCOV) amplitude signal. Simultaneously, the islanding triggering signal transitions sharply from logic level 0 to 1, indicating that islanding has been successfully identified. This triggering signal is sent to the circuit breaker control unit, which responds immediately by opening the circuit to isolate the distributed generation unit from the grid. As a result, the PCC voltage magnitude drops to zero volts post-0.5 seconds, ensuring that the system is safely disconnected and preventing unsafe back-feeding or equipment damage. The coordination between the ROCOCV

passive detection, triggering logic, and breaker operation confirms the effectiveness of the proposed method in accurately detecting islanding events and protecting the system with minimal delay.

Simulation Results of Islanding Detection and Protection Operation

VII. Conclusion

In this paper, a novel passive islanding detection method combined with overvoltage and overcurrent protection mechanisms is proposed to mitigate islanding risks in grid-connected renewable energy systems. The integration of voltage and current disturbance monitoring with threshold-based detection algorithms enhances the system's ability to accurately and swiftly detect islanding conditions, significantly reducing the non-detection zone (NDZ) compared to conventional passive methods. The results from MATLAB/Simulink simulations demonstrate that the proposed approach offers enhanced sensitivity, improved response time, and better adaptability to fluctuating grid conditions. This approach ensures compliance with IEEE 1547 and

IEC 62116 standards by detecting islanding events within a few milliseconds, thus ensuring grid stability and operational safety. The combined use of passive detection and advanced protection circuits provides a cost-effective solution for preventing equipment damage and minimizing power quality issues during islanding conditions. Additionally, the integration of overvoltage and overcurrent protection mechanisms reduces the likelihood of transient overvoltages and overcurrents that can lead to equipment failures. The proposed method represents a significant advancement in islanding detection, offering a reliable, efficient, and low-cost solution for enhancing the safety and stability of grid-connected renewable energy systems.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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